

RealWorld Systems Inc.

Performance Measurement System Design Document

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PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM DESIGN DOCUMENT

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1. Objective and Audience

The objective of this document is to propose an overall design for an organizational performance measurement system that will enable each business unit to ‘plug in’ their own performance indicators while providing a coherent framework for the Board and senior management to manage performance for the organization as a whole.

The expected users of this report are:

- Senior management – for sections 1-3
- Staff with responsibilities for managing performance in each business unit – for the entire report including appendices
- Board and volunteers will be presented with a slide deck that will summarize the main points

2. Proposed Design for a Performance Measurement System

This proposed performance measurement system (MS) will be anchored at the Board level with an Executive Dashboard that will be reported every three months and have the following characteristics:

- The Dashboard will list 6 core organizational objectives that the agency needs to monitor in order to manage performance against its mission (see Appendix D).
- The objectives in the Dashboard will be based on the mission statement and current strategy, and will be derived from an organizational logic model (see Appendix C).
- For each core objective, the Dashboard will define a set of key performance indicators, performance against minimum targets, the maturity of its major business processes, and key actions to be carried out in the following quarter (see Appendix E).
- Minimum (and possibly desired) targets for each indicator will be approved by the Board after an annual target setting process that involves the relevant Board committees (see Appendix E).
- Core objectives will be reviewed and updated whenever the strategic plan is changed, or as necessary.
- The Dashboard will be designed to report performance in a way that ties directly to process improvement and human resource management (see Appendix G).
- To maximize the speed of implementation, the Dashboard will be designed to allow for the development of processes to guide the collection and analysis of certain performance results simultaneous to the reporting of those results. This is accomplished by allowing a “*Target not defined or information not available*” status to appear in the Dashboard (see Appendix E - key).
- The Dashboard will be distributed to all new staff and consultants along with the Mission and

current strategic priorities to ensure that their work is consistent with the agency's core business objectives and key performance indicators.

The advantages of this approach are:

- The prominence of the Dashboard, and in particular the requirement that its targets be annually approved by the Board, will ensure that the agency's performance measurement system delivers data that are meaningful to the Board and that lead directly to improvements. Meanwhile, the technical complexity of the underlying analyses will be available to those who wish to grapple with the various logic models, evaluation frameworks, market studies, financial statements, research methodologies and so on. Each business unit can select indicators that derive from their own disciplines, and need not use the same vocabulary across the whole organization.
- Programs and initiatives will be designed to contribute to the objectives and indicators that are most important to the agency. Priorities, objectives and assumptions will be clarified at the beginning of major initiatives rather than when they are almost completed. At the annual process of target-setting, Board committees and senior management will define what they mean by 'Return on Investment' and 'winning results' through a process of negotiating minimum and desired results for specific investments and programs. Some unrealistic expectations will be clarified immediately, and others will be identified and corrected as the initiatives progress.
- New programs will define their targets in the context of the relevant organization-level objectives and indicators. If there is a poor match between a program's objectives and the agency's key performance indicators, senior management may either question the priority of the new program/initiative, or recommend a change of core objectives and/or indicators to the appropriate Board committee and thence to the Board.
- The inclusion of business processes in the Dashboard will enable the agency to identify high-priority processes in need of improvement and prevent the high risk behaviour that often results from an over-emphasis on a small number of performance targets. Process maturity ensures that corporate values are maintained and that unexpected information is gathered and responded to.
- The inclusion of 'actions in the next 3 months' in the Dashboard will enable the agency to prioritize needed improvements, allocate the resources necessary to realize those improvements and monitor improvement progress. This information will furthermore make it possible to hold programs accountable for demonstrating good management and for demonstrating how performance information is used to improve. At the same time, because facilitating improvement is the key objective of the system, the usefulness of the performance measurement system itself can be evaluated by noting the number and type of improvements made.
- The information architecture represented by the Dashboard is practical in that only the most important information is collected and communicated to key stakeholders at limited time intervals. The relative simplicity of the design gives the agency the opportunity to:
 - Ensure that the time span for implementing the MS is realistic and that expectations are well managed
 - Focus on the factors critical to successful implementation of a performance measurement system (see Section 3)

- Test the system’s overall effectiveness before expending resources to build a more comprehensive and therefore more complex system
- Ensure that staff have sufficient resources to learn and put into practice the new skills they will need to fulfill their MS-related responsibilities

Figure 1 shows how the Executive Dashboard will be one of the three central planning documents at the agency, along with the Mission and current Strategy. The technical material and analyses would be ‘under the water line’ and not typically reported to the Board.

Figure 1: Central planning documents – Mission, Strategy and Executive Dashboard

3. Critical Success Factors

The success of the agency’s performance measurement system will rely on the extent to which it can achieve five critical tasks:

1. Establish accountability for performance
2. Build capacity to analyze performance data and to manage for improvement
3. Focus on the needs of key stakeholders
4. Ensure visible and consistent involvement by its leadership
5. Evaluate the effectiveness of the MS and refine it over time

Establish accountability for performance

Successful deployment of the performance measurement system at the agency will be strongly tied to development of a system of accountability whereby the agency staff and volunteers 'buy in' to performance measurement by assuming responsibility for their parts of the process.

Terms of Reference and Job Descriptions at the agency should be updated to reflect the following general areas of accountability:

- The Board should be responsible for approving annual performance targets and for ensuring that the structure and format of the Executive Dashboard meets its needs and requirements.
- The CEO, senior management and certain Board committees at the agency should be responsible for establishing strategic and business unit plans, resource allocations and indicators that are tied to the core organizational objectives.
- The CEO and Board should hold programs accountable for demonstrating good management and for demonstrating how performance information is used to improve.
- The CEO, Board and senior management should be responsible for establishing policies that institutionalize problem-solving approaches for poor performance and should be responsible for establishing policies that reward programs and individuals that can document areas in which they improve.
- The CEO and Board should be responsible for ensuring that appropriate staff have sufficient resources to learn and put into practice the new skills they will need to fulfill their MS-related responsibilities.
- Senior management, the CFO, the Finance Committee and the CEO should be responsible for ensuring that budgets and plans are tied directly and explicitly to the agency's core objectives.
- Staff at varying levels of the organization's hierarchy (e.g., VPs, managers, front-line staff, etc.) should be responsible for the management of individual processes and measures (i.e., the measurement and process owners).
- Managers should be responsible for ensuring that performance goals are met by rating individual contributions to performance goals in their staff's individual performance appraisals.
- A staff member should be assigned to manage and coordinate the development, implementation and maintenance of the agency's Performance Management System. This staff

member or his/her designee should develop and seek approval for [a] work plans to guide the staged development of the MS and [b] procedures that ensure the quality, reliability and timeliness of reported performance data.

Build capacity to analyze performance data and to manage for improvement

A performance measurement system is effective when it is used by staff for planning and management purposes, to determine if things are on track, and to serve as an early warning system - raising questions and pointing to areas that may require more in-depth attention¹ and ultimately to improve. However it is critical to realize that this sort of capacity is not automatically obtained just by collecting and reporting performance data. In fact, even deciding what data to collect and how and when to collect it is not a trivial task.

The agency needs to develop capacity in all stages of the performance measurement and management process. To do so, it must develop approaches for capacity building so that staff can learn what data to collect and how to analyze and make use of it. For example, staff can build analytic capacity through guided practice - by attempting to understand performance data in context, by looking for performance trends and by attempting to discover and fix the underlying causes for poor performance.

Figure 4 shows the various stages for performance measurement and management where building sufficient capacity will be critical for success:

Figure 2: Different stages of the measurement and management process form a continuous loop

Focus on the needs of key stakeholders

The agency needs to identify its top priority stakeholders and then focus on meeting their needs and requirements. For example, developing a volunteer and donor focus would require the agency to find

¹ Perrin, B. (1999). Performance Measurement: Does the reality match the rhetoric? A rejoinder to Bernstein and Winston. *American Journal of Evaluation*. 20(1).

out what volunteers and donors want and expect, and then to use that information in every aspect of its operations. For example:

- **Performance data should be used to design and improve products, services and processes.**
 - What key donor needs exist that are not currently being met? Are new products or services necessary?
 - Are there products, services or activities that have little or no value to key stakeholders, in particular volunteers and donors?
 - How well do current products and services meet donors' and volunteers' essential needs?
 - Do the agency priorities match all of its stakeholders' priorities? When there are irreconcilable conflicts between stakeholder priorities, which are most important?
 - What are the requirements for new or redesigned programs from donors' and volunteers' points of view?
 - What do donors and volunteers say are acceptable levels of performance, and are they satisfied?
- **Stakeholder related data should be used to obtain, retain or optimize resources.**
 - Are the agency's accomplishments successfully communicated to donors and volunteers?
 - Are donors and volunteers satisfied with the information they receive?
 - Do staff members understand how their work contributes to meeting donor and funder needs?
 - Are skill sets aligned around the needs of donors and volunteers?
 - Are well functioning information systems in place?
 - Are staffing levels in key areas optimal?

The agency should use the performance measurement system as a lever for becoming a stakeholder-centric organization.

Ensure visible and consistent involvement by the agency's leadership

Visible and consistent involvement by the agency's leadership through *promotion*, *institutionalization* and *use* is critical to the successful implementation of the performance measurement system².

Promotion involves developing a set of key messages (e.g., why the MS is being developed, how it will be used, etc.) and routinely delivering these messages to staff using a variety of communication channels (e.g., internal newsletters, standing agenda items in meetings, retreats, etc.). Appendix B provides a brief conceptual framework that in combination with Section 1 (above) may be helpful for developing key messages.

Institutionalization means translating the vision for the system into reality, by, for example:

- Defining the performance information to be reported to whom and when

² Moynihan, D.P. & Ingraham, P.W. (2004). Integrative leadership in the public sector: a model of performance-information use. *Administration & Society*. 36(4).

- Assessing performance information quality and credibility
- Creating or modifying policies and procedures to ensure appropriate use, and so on.

Use means that the agency's leadership actually use the system when running the organization. In doing so, leaders model its value and importance to the rest of the staff.

Evaluate the effectiveness of the MS and refine it over time

There are many challenges associated with designing and implementing an effective performance measurement system³. Many organizations spend a significant amount of time and money to build performance measurement systems that never realize the expected benefits. This is often because organizations do not see performance measurement as a *system*. Systems are made up of people, processes and technology. To successfully implement performance measurement an organization *must* focus on developing all three components simultaneously as too great a focus on any one component will lead to failure.

To accomplish an 'even' development, the agency should build up the system in stages ensuring 'good enough' levels of each component (i.e., capacity to use the system, procedures to guide related work, and technology to support the system). As each stage is implemented, the agency should spend at least a year to evaluate the overall effectiveness of the system and refine it based on careful consideration of what is working and what is not, who is satisfied and who is not and so on.

As an example of staged system development, Appendix F shows a sample dashboard for a single business unit. It may be that the use of similar dashboards for all business units be mandated (i.e., standardized across all business units) in later stages of performance measurement system development.

³ The literature is replete with examples. See references in Powers, L.C. (2009). A framework for evaluating the effectiveness of performance measurement systems. *RealWorld Systems Research Series 2009:1*. Available at SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1371158>

Appendix A: Requirements for the Executive Dashboard

The following are known requirements for performance reporting through the Executive Dashboard at the agency. Additional requirements will surface as the system is implemented and used.

General Requirements for the Executive Dashboard

1. The Executive Dashboard should be:
 - Structured around the core objectives of the organization
 - Include one or more indicators for each objective
 - Include an underlying operational definition for each indicator that describes:
 - the intent of the indicator
 - the indicator's role in achieving the performance goal
 - when, how and by whom indicator data will be collected
 - guidance for interpreting the indicator (as necessary)
2. The Executive Dashboard should be useful. The Dashboard will be considered useful when it meets the known needs of the customer as described below in draft.
3. The Executive Dashboard should be of high-quality. The Dashboard will be considered high-quality when it meets the recipient stakeholder's known requirements as described below in draft.
4. The data reported should be of high quality. Data is considered to be of high-quality when it is credible, reliable and timely. Where data (or data sources) are weak then performance reports should describe the weaknesses. Transparency regarding weaknesses increases credibility.
5. For each core objective, it is required that reports include one or more key performance indicators, performance against minimum targets, a maturity rating for related processes, and key actions to be carried out within the next 3 months.

Key Stakeholder Roles, Needs and Requirements for the Executive Dashboard

Board

Role (Customer):

The Board is accountable for setting policy and making decisions about the overall direction and strategy of the organization in accordance with its mission, vision, business objectives, and stakeholder commitments.

Needs:

- The agency's Board of Directors needs clear and informative quarterly reports to monitor the organization's overall performance against core organizational objectives (including strategic sub-objectives and priorities) in order to satisfy due diligence responsibilities and enable it to set appropriate directions for the organization.

Requirements:

- Performance reports for the Board should take the form of an Executive Dashboard that is brief (1 to 4 pages in length).
- The Executive Dashboard should be easy to read, have a look and feel that satisfies the Board, and should be intuitive and easy to use. Board members should be able to understand the contents of the Executive Dashboard with minimal orientation.
- The Executive Dashboard should be delivered to the Board at least 1.5 weeks prior to each scheduled Board meeting where organizational performance is on the agenda (we suggest quarterly).

Chief Executive Officer (CEO)

Role⁴ (Customer):

The CEO is responsible for carrying out the strategic plans and policies of the organization. The CEO:

- Supports the operations and administration of the Board
- Oversees design, marketing, promotion, delivery and quality of programs, products and services
- Recommends yearly budgets for Board approval and prudently manages organization's resources within budget guidelines
- Effectively manages the human resources of the organization
- Assures the organization and its mission, programs, products and services are consistently presented in strong, positive image to relevant stakeholders
- Oversees fundraising planning and implementation

⁴ This description is paraphrased from the Free Management Library's suggested functions and responsibilities for executives of nonprofit organizations at http://www.managementhelp.org/chf_exec/ed_defn.htm

Needs:

- The CEO needs to be able to monitor the organization's overall performance against core organizational objectives including strategic sub-objectives and priorities in order to ensure that resources are appropriately assigned and that progress against mission is being achieved.

Requirements:

- CEO requirements for the Dashboard are the same as those for the Board (see above)

Standing Board Committee Responsible for Mission [Mission Committee]

Role (Customer):

[Copy from the committee's terms of reference]

Needs:

- The Mission Committee should be able to use the Executive Dashboard to:
 - Spot areas for potential improvement
 - Spot early indications of trouble (e.g., misuse of data, gaming)
 - Raise questions regarding Mission performance and point to areas that may require more in-depth evaluation or study

Requirements:

- The Dashboard should be delivered to the Mission Committee at least 1.5 weeks prior to each scheduled Committee meeting where Mission performance is on the agenda.

Senior Mission Managers

Role (Suppliers):

Senior Mission Managers are responsible for meeting key performance targets for their functional areas, programs and projects. They ensure that there are adequate links between core organizational objectives and their staff's performance objectives.

Senior Mission Managers supply information to the Executive Dashboard. In the early stages of system development, Senior Managers will supply this information via departmental, program and project level budgets, plans and/or evaluation frameworks, often in cooperation with the Program / Project Administrators that report to them.

Program / Project Administrators

Role (Suppliers):

Program administrators are responsible for meeting key performance targets for their programs and projects.

Program / Project Administrators supply information to the Executive Dashboard through their program and project level budgets, plans and/or evaluation frameworks in cooperation with their Managers.

Other stakeholders for the Executive Dashboard include:

- Various agency Committees (e.g., Finance Committee)
- Chief Financial Officer (CFO)
- Vice Presidents or Directors for Human Resources, Marketing, Fundraising

Appendix B: Conceptual Framework

The following concepts are central to understanding the roles that successful performance measurement should play at the agency:

- Performance measurement is a key component of evidence-informed performance management.
- Performance management as an activity seeks to improve performance at the individual, program, business unit and organization levels using performance data (as opposed to intuition) to inform action.
- The ideal situation for the agency (or for any organization) is to have everyone working towards the achievement of the same objectives.
- Objectives are cascaded down through an organization while results flow up.

The following diagram⁵ illustrates these concepts:

Figure 3: How performance measurement links to action

⁵ Adapted from Dransfield, R. (2000). *Human Resource Management - Studies in Economics and Business*. Heinemann Educational Publishers.

A performance measurement system can lead to greater effectiveness only if it is evidence informed, and fully embedded into the management and improvement processes of the organization. The following diagram⁶ shows the relationship between performance measurement and management capacity in an organization:

Figure 4: A black box conceptualization of performance management

⁶ Adapted from the black box model for performance management, Moynihan, D.P. & Ingraham, P.W. (2004). Integrative leadership in the public sector: a model of performance-information use. *Administration & Society*. 36(4).

Appendix C: Logic Model

Insert organizational logic model

Appendix D: Core Organizational Objectives

Following is a list of 6 proposed core organizational objectives based on the functions that all human service agencies must manage.

Core Objective	Description
1. Mission statement	Enable the x through y. (Another core objective may be necessary if the agency has a two-part mission statement.)
2. Uphold the agency's reputation and build its brand equity	[Description may be written by marketing business unit.]
3. Increase net revenue	Increase the dollars going towards mission activities.
4. Manage performance	Strategically manage performance to maximize efficiency, productivity and effectiveness.
5. Achieve stakeholder satisfaction	Understand, engage and meet the needs of the stakeholders who are important in achieving the mission.
6. Maintain good governance	Systematically set and monitor organizational strategy and objectives, and ensure that appropriate actions are taken to maintain the agency's adherence to its mission and values.

Appendix E: Executive Dashboard (Template)

Objective	Process Status	Months at Current Status	Key Performance Indicators [Examples]	Result Status	Months at Current Status	Actions in next 3 months [Examples]
1. [Re-stating of agency's mission]		0 0 0	<p>Define objectives, milestones and minimum targets for each activity</p> <p>Decide on which medium/emerging priorities should be reported at Executive Dashboard level</p>			
2. Uphold the agency's reputation and build its brand equity		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Results of public opinion survey (or whatever is used by the agency) compared to previous year +/- competitors Content analysis of media tracking and real-time web searches, including social media 		0	
3. Increase net revenue		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase in total revenues compared to previous years % of the agency dollars allocated to mission activities benchmarked against competitors+/- or previous years Reduction in non-value-added mission activity costs (\$ saved) in previous 12 months 		0	
4. Manage performance		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # and status of planned improvement projects # and results of implemented improvement projects (with qualitative description and/or quantitative data if available) 		0	
5. Achieve stakeholder satisfaction		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donor satisfaction with mission activities Content analysis of complaints from all stakeholders 		0	

Objective	Process Status	Months at Current Status	Key Performance Indicators [Examples]	Result Status	Months at Current Status	Actions in next 3 months [Examples]
			regarding all activities			
6. Maintain good governance		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Board satisfaction with Executive Dashboard targets, reports and follow-up actions Succession plans for upcoming board retirements 		0	

Rating Key for Dashboard

PROCESSES: Are processes in place to manage performance toward this objective?	RESULT: Was the objective met?
Did not meet minimum target(s) for at least one key performance indicator	
Met or exceeded minimum targets for most key performance indicators, and for all essential indicators	
Met or exceeded desired targets for some key performance indicators while achieving minimum results for all of them.	
Months at current status: Number of months that the traffic light colour has stayed the same.	Targets not defined or information not available

Appendix F: Example Business Unit Dashboard

This dashboard captures indicators and targets for mission activities only, in each of the 6 core objectives. Some of these indicators – marked with [1] will be rolled up to the Executive Dashboard. Each program or project will have its own objectives, indicators and milestones that will be summarized in this mission-level dashboard.

CORE OBJECTIVE 1: Enable x through y

Sub-Objectives	Core Processes	Process Maturity	Key Performance Indicators	Minimum Target	Result	Actions
<p>1.1. Annual plans are formally documented and include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference to appropriate research or theoretical underpinnings • Reference to specific target audiences and their needs and requirements • Reference to applicable assessments (e.g., policy analysis or community evaluations) that establish a need for the planned intervention(s) • Activity level SMART objectives, definition of success, outcome measures, targets, data sources, resource needs, budgets and major milestones • Relationship to the agency's core business objectives 	<p>Annual Mission planning procedure</p> <p>Includes or interfaces with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual priority setting procedure • Assessment procedure(s) • Annual departmental (or functional) level budgeting and planning procedure • 3-5 year strategic planning procedure 		<p>Assess the plan for each high/Board focused priority mission activity. If it does not have a solid rationale based on policy and research, decide whether to develop a rationale, or phase it out, or analyze it under another objective (e.g., fundraising, brand equity).</p> <p>Assess the plan for each high/Board focused priority mission activity. If it does not have SMART objectives and milestones, develop them.</p>			

1.2. Mission activities are implemented according to plan and are meeting specified milestones and objectives	Quality assurance / control procedures Performance monitoring / reporting procedures		% of activities meeting specified objectives and milestones ⁷ [1] # public policies changed or policy agendas moved in past 12 months (list and one-sentence summary) [1]	Each activity should have interim reports that include progress against milestones.		Assess each mission activity. If it is not being delivered at a quality and amount that is meaningful in relation to the objectives, it should either obtain adequate resources, or be phased out, or analyzed under another objective (e.g., brand equity or fundraising)
1.3. High priority activities are monitored and periodically reported to key stakeholders including the Board and Committees	Performance monitoring / reporting procedures					Define minimum targets for each program that will be rolled up to the Executive Dashboard and reported quarterly

CORE OBJECTIVE 2: Uphold the agency's reputation and build its brand equity

Sub-objectives	Core Processes	Process Maturity	Key Performance Indicators	Minimum Target	Result	Actions
2.1. Output and outcomes for Mission activities are selected to demonstrate the agency's effectiveness and efficiency	Performance monitoring / reporting procedures		Stories and measures incorporated into marketing and fundraising material			

CORE OBJECTIVE 3: Increase net revenue - Increase the dollars going towards mission activities.

Sub-objectives	Core Processes	Process Maturity	Key Performance Indicators	Minimum Target	Result	Actions
3.1. Mission activities	Performance monitoring /		% of the agency dollars allocated			

⁷ Mission staff need to decide what the denominator of this percentage is: Does it include only the projects that have fully developed plans meeting the requirements in objective 1.1, or would it include all high/board focused projects, or would it include all defined activities?

contribute to increased net revenue through the reduction of non-value added costs	reporting procedures Interfaces with: • Annual budgeting and planning procedures		to Mission activities benchmarked against competitors +/- previous years [1] Mission \$ spent YTD compared to plan Reduction in non-value-added Mission activity costs (\$ saved) in previous 12 months [1]			
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CORE OBJECTIVE 4: Manage performance - Strategically manage performance to maximize efficiency, productivity and effectiveness.

Sub-objectives	Core Processes	Process Maturity	Key Performance Indicators	Minimum Target	Result	Actions
4.1. Mission management demonstrates that it analyzes and interprets performance data to: • Highlight deficiencies and issues that require further exploration • Plan, implement and report on improvements that maximize efficiency, productivity and/or effectiveness	Performance monitoring / reporting procedures Continuous process improvement process		# of deficiencies and issues identified that require further exploration and/or # of evaluations or studies planned # and status of planned improvement projects [1] # and results of implemented improvement projects (with qualitative description of and/or quantitative data if available)[1]			

CORE OBJECTIVE 5: Achieve stakeholder satisfaction - Understand, engage and meet the needs of the stakeholders who are important in achieving the mission.

Sub-objectives	Core Processes	Process Maturity	Key Performance Indicators	Minimum Target	Result	Actions
5.1. All mission procedures contain elements related to	Stakeholder satisfaction procedures		Key stakeholder satisfaction with mission activities (define key			

<p>the identification of stakeholders, stakeholder engagement, stakeholder needs and requirements assessments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Includes instructions for how to systematically obtain stakeholder needs, requirements, feedback, etc. Ways to use information- e.g., stakeholder satisfaction levels can be used to test presumed cause and effect relationships between performance and objectives or outcomes 		<p>stakeholder group) [1]</p> <p>Content analysis of complaints from all stakeholders regarding all activities [1]</p>			
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CORE OBJECTIVE 6: Maintain good governance - Systematically set and monitor organizational strategy and objectives, and ensure that appropriate actions are taken to maintain the agency's adherence to its mission and values.

Sub-objectives	Core Processes	Process Maturity	Key Performance Indicators	Minimum Target	Result	Actions
<p>6.1. Mission reports to board on core objectives</p>	<p>Performance monitoring / reporting procedures</p>		<p>Mission committee and Board satisfaction with Executive Dashboard targets, reports and follow-up actions related to Mission activities [1]</p>			

Appendix G: Template for Process Responsibilities

This table presents a table for listing core processes that relate to each objective, along with major staff roles. This table would be populated in future phases of the performance measurement system and is included to show how the Executive Dashboard links to the Human Resources staff measurement system through the assignment of responsibilities to core processes .

Core Objectives (Persons responsible)	Core Related Processes	Process Owner	Customer(s)	Supplier(s)
1. Enable x through y (CEO and Mission VP)	Name key process	Name of manager	<i>Internal:</i> <i>External:</i>	<i>Internal:</i> <i>External:</i>
	Other processes	TBD	TBD	TBD
3. Uphold the agency's reputation and build its brand equity (CEO and Marketing VP)	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD